

The phase transitions of methylammonium bromobismuthates $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ and $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_{11}$

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The phase transitions of methylammonium bromobismuthates $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ and $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_{11}$ have been confirmed and investigated by Raman spectroscopy. Major structural and dynamical changes occur due to the low temperature phase transitions. The Raman spectra below the transition temperatures are marked by appearance of new bands as well as change of intensities and band shapes.

Phase transitions is an important area of investigation in Solid State Chemistry and Solid State Physics. The main purpose of such investigations is to determine the microscopic order-parameter¹⁻³. Laser Raman spectroscopy has been proved very useful for the purpose although a variety of other techniques like Brillouin scattering, inelastic neutron scattering are required to get a more complete picture of the dynamics within a solid².

Alkylammonium salts undergo interesting phase transitions generally involving hydrogen bonding as well as reorientational motions of the alkylammonium ions⁴⁻⁷. Phase transitions in alkylammonium halogenoantimonates and bismuthates have been described in the literature⁸. Infrared and Raman spectroscopic investigations on methyl ammonium halogenoantimonates(III), $[\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_{4-n}\text{H}_n]_3\text{Sb}_2\text{X}_9$ ($n=0-3$, X = Cl or Br) through their phase transitions were reported by us⁹. The ferroelectric phase transition of $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_{11}$ was also followed by Raman spectroscopy¹⁰. Phase transitions were detected at low temperatures in $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ and $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_5$

$\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_{11}$ from dielectric measurements^{11,13}. In the present work Raman spectroscopy has been used to confirm the occurrence and to investigate nature of these phase transitions. The study indicates that the low-temperature phase transitions at 101 K in $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ and at 77 K in $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_{11}$ appear to involve a displacive mechanism in contrast to the phase transitions at higher temperatures wherein the mechanism is mainly the orientational order-disorder of the methylammonium cations.

Results and discussion

$(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$: The crystal structure of this compound isomorphous to $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ is described by $P\bar{3}$ ml space group with $a = 0.807$, $c = 1.008$ nm and $Z = 1$ ¹¹. The structure involves a framework of polymeric $\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9^{3-}$ anion with CH_3NH_3^+ cations in the cavities⁸. A dielectric anomaly was detected while cooling the sample at 101.5 K and the phase below this temperature was reported to be improper ferroelectric¹¹. The Raman spectra across the 101 K transition are shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen that new

Fig. 1. Raman spectra of $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ across the phase transition.

Table 1. Raman bands of $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ across the transition at 101 K		
300 K	10 K	Assignment
–	3192 w	asym NH_3 stretch
3182 m	3176 m	
–	3146 m	sym NH_3 stretch
3130 m	3113 m	
3048 m	3041 m	asym CH_3 stretch
2973 vs	2969 vs	sym CH_3 stretch
2833 w	2825 w	–
1590 m	1592 m	asym NH_3 deformation
–	1578 m	
1477 s	1468 s	asym CH_3 deformation
–	1457 s	
1425 m	1425 m	sym CH_3 deformation
1264 w	1255 m	rocking
–	977 s	C–N stretch
971 s	971	
919 m	915 vs	rocking
–	380 m	CH_3NH_3^+ torsion
355 m	360	
–	278 m	?
190 vs	193 vs	Bi–Br stretch (terminal)
164 s	167 s	Bi–Br stretch (bridging)
–	141 w	Lattice modes
72 w	76 w	
52 s	59 s	
–	48 w	
–	39w	
30 w	30 w	

bands appear in the low-temperature phase. Appearance of new bands and change of intensities indicate a major structural reorganization. The band positions are listed in Table 1. A new band appears around 278 cm^{-1} . The band around 355 cm^{-1} splits. There is a marked change in the intensity of the band around 919 cm^{-1} . The bands at 971 , 1477 , 1590 , 3130 and 3182 cm^{-1} also split.

$(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_{11}$: Jakubas reported the formation of this compound¹². The compound crystallises in orthorhombic symmetry with $a = 13.431$, $b = 14.468$, $c = 16.033$ and $Z = 4$. The crystal is built up of methylammonium cations and isolated $\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_{11}^{5-}$ groups. The $\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_{11}^{5-}$ anion consists of two octahedra joined via one bromine bridge. The compound undergoes phase transitions at 312 K and 77 K ¹³. It is interesting to note that while the 312 K transition is accompanied by a minor change in the Raman spectrum¹⁰, there is a complete modification of the Raman spectrum across the 77 K transition. The spectra are shown in Fig. 2 and a listing of all the Raman modes with their assignment is given in Table 2. The bi-octahedral anion $\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_{11}^{5-}$ contains two types of Bi–Br bonds, terminal and bridging. The terminal and bridging Bi–Br stretches occur at 186 and 164 cm^{-1} respectively. Below the transition temperature a new band appears at 285 cm^{-1} . All bands split in the range 900 – 3300 cm^{-1} except C–N stretch.

The spectra of these compounds suggest major changes in structural organisation at low temperatures. More specifically they indicate increase in the number of molecular units per unit cell and a displacive mechanism for these transitions. On the other hand high temperature transitions are related mainly to orientational ordering/disordering of methylammonium cations. Techniques such as Brillouin scattering and inelastic neutron scattering can throw more

Fig. 2. Raman spectra of $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_{11}$ across the phase transition.

Table 2. Raman bands of $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_{11}$ across the transition at 77 K

300 K	10 K	Assignment
-	3243 m	asym NH_3 stretch
-	3208 m	
3180 m	3185 w	
-	3165 m	
-	3138 m	
-	3123 w	sym NH_3 stretch
3114 m	3098 s	
-	3095	asym CH_3 stretch
-	3063 m	
3042 m	3043 m	
-	3034 s	sym CH_3 stretch
2970 s	2971 vs	
-	2967 sh	
-	2945 m	-
2892 w	2898 w	
2822 w	2820 m	
-	2811 m	
1592 m	1595 s	asym NH_3 deformation
-	1579 s	
-	1573 s	
1482 m	1489	asym CH_3 deformation
-	1477	
-	1468 s	
1460 sh	1456	
-	1450	sym CH_3 deformation
1420 m	1422 m	
-	1418	rocking
1260 w	1260 m	
-	1252	C-N stretch
975 s	976 s	
-	931	rocking
921 m	915 m	
-	910	
-	285 m	?
186 vs	192 vs	Bi-Br stretch (terminal)
-	170	Bi-Br stretch (bridging)
164 sh	164 s	
-	157	Bi-Br deformation
144 sh	150	
-	135	
-	123 w	
-	109	

-	85	} Lattice modes
-	75	
68	65 m	
54 m	60	
-	43	
-	31	

vs-very strong, s-strong, m-medium, w-weak, sh-shoulder.

light on the type of phonons driving the phase transitions.

Experimental

The compounds were prepared by the reaction of stoichiometric quantities of CH_3NH_2 , Bi_2O_3 and HBr in aqueous solution. The yellow crystals are obtained on slow evaporation. The materials were characterised by their IR and Raman spectra as well as DSC. The spectra of powdered samples were recorded on a Spex 1403 Laser Raman spectrometer using the 514.5 nm line of a Spectra Physics argon laser. Air products cryogenic refrigeration system was used for obtaining spectra at low temperatures.

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